

Stage 2: Interview Question Guide

For Stage 2 of the semi-structured interview study reported in the paper “What You See is What You Trace - A Two-Stage Interview Study on Traceability Practices and Eye Tracking Potential”

As the interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner and interviewees naturally differ in the elaborateness of their answers, these questions only serve as a guide to follow for interviewers. When answers are too broad, follow-up questions are needed. On the other hand, when certain questions were already answered in previous responses, these can also be omitted.

We added short italic notes below questions whenever the quantitative or qualitative extent of the expected answer is not self-explanatory.

Introduction and Background

1. Introduction of the interviewer: briefly explain content and structure of the interview, anonymous analysis of responses and right to cancel or request data deletion at any time
2. Do you agree with this interview being recorded?
3. Please describe your role and tasks concerning software projects.

Codes: **Demographics**

4. How long (in years) have you been working in or with software projects?
5. *The description of the person’s role should clarify how the interviewee is involved in the requirements management process of the projects they work in.*

Codes: **Demographics**

6. How long have you been working in this project?

Codes: **Demographics**

Part 1: Requirements Management

7. Which artifact types do you work with? (e.g., textual requirements, models, UML, user stories, project plan, code, tests, etc.)

Codes: **Artifact Types**

8. Which tools do you use during a normal work day?
When tools like a Git wiki are mentioned, a follow-up question is needed to find out what kind of information is stored in that wiki.
 - a. Which of these tools do you use how much if you only consider “productive” working time (excluding meetings)? If you had to put percentage numbers on them?

Codes: **Artifact Types**

Tools to manage / store Requirements

9. Is there a specific “workflow” when you are working with requirements?
This question focuses on how the different artifact types are used in the whole process and what purpose they serve.

Codes: **Artifact Types**
Tools to manage / store Requirements
Screen Space Usage

10. Which document types or artifacts do you often use in parallel? I.e., one is accessed directly after the other or both are shown on the screen simultaneously.

Codes: **Artifact Types**
Tools to manage / store Requirements
Screen Space Usage

Part 2: Traceability Practices, Benefits and Problems

11. How is traceability implemented in this project?
This question is one of the focal points of this interview. Let the interviewee elaborate on their own first, but make sure the following aspects are covered and ask for details when necessary. The response should describe the artifacts types that are traced, what the traces are used for and by whom.

- a. If not sure what the term means, give short explanation.
 - i. Software Traceability is defined as the ability to link together related artifacts from different sources within a project.
 - ii. Traceability of requirements is the ability to describe and follow the life of a requirement in both a forwards and backwards direction.
 - iii. Its advantages include requirements coverage analysis, change impact analysis or dependency analysis.
- b. In what way? What is traced? Are there different types of links? Which granularity?
- c. How much manual effort is required? Is it implemented for the entire project or only certain parts?
- d. How well does it work? Are there any problems like poorly maintained or missing links?

Codes: **Artifact Types**
Tools to manage / store Requirements
Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability
Concerns with Eye Tracking Traceability
Currently linked Artifact Types
Perceived Tracing Purpose

12. Are you using any of these trace links? If yes, how? For what purpose?

Codes: **Artifact Types**
Tools to manage / store Requirements
Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability
Concerns with Eye Tracking Traceability
Perceived Tracing Purpose

13. What is your personal opinion regarding traceability? Do you think that the benefits outweigh the costs?

Codes: **Artifact Types**
Tools to manage / store Requirements
Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability
Concerns with Eye Tracking Traceability
Perceived Tracing Purpose

Part 3: Tracing with Eye Tracking

14. The next questions are asked in a more open way. For that I will explain a new approach for the automatic detection of trace links by using eye tracking. The idea is that eye tracking data are automatically recorded while people – may it be requirements engineers, architects, developers or testers – normally work on their tasks. By unintrusively recording gaze data in the background, it can be detected which artifacts are often looked at consecutively. Thereby, links are being generated between those artifacts. This way, when looking at that artifact again you can directly access related ones by following these detected links. E.g., when you look at a JIRA ticket, then at a part of a specification page and then to another related document, this gaze path could be processed to trace links between those artifacts.

15. Do you have any questions about the approach? Did you understand the concept? Did anything remain unclear?

Codes: **General Opinion on Eye Tracking Traceability**
Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability
Concern with Eye Tracking Traceability

16. Generally speaking: what do you think of the approach? Do you see a use for it? Do you have any concerns?

This question is the most important one in the interview and usually leads to a quite extensive answer. Focus on potential use cases and potential obstacles for the approach.

Codes: **General Opinion on Eye Tracking Traceability**
Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability
Concern with Eye Tracking Traceability

17. Do you see a use case for this approach for the way you personally work?
- e. Would it be possible to detect useful links based on gaze data recorded during your tasks?
 - f. Would any of these detected links be useful for your tasks?

Codes: **General Opinion on Eye Tracking Traceability**
Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability
Concern with Eye Tracking Traceability
Factors influencing ET-Link Usefulness

18. Would you prefer that these links are shown to you as suggestions, i.e., when you often look between certain artifacts, a dialog comes up and asks if you want to create a link between these two? Or would you prefer for it to be done completely automatically even though there might be incorrect links included as well which you would need to correct later on?

Codes: **Suggestions or Automation**

19. Would you prefer to only have your own gaze data processed to links or also see the implicitly created links of others?

Codes: **Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability**
Concern with Eye Tracking Traceability

20. Do you think that it might make sense to collect links in a context-sensitive manner? I.e., that links depend on the person's role or the task that they were working on while the trace link was collected?

Codes: **Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability**
Concern with Eye Tracking Traceability

21. Could you see yourself having an eye tracker running while you are working or would you have concerns regarding privacy and observation?

Interviewees should not only state yes or no, but also why they would use an eye tracker or what would hold them back.

- g. Which preconditions would need to be fulfilled for you to feel comfortable with detecting trace links based on gaze data?

Codes: **Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability**
Concern with Eye Tracking Traceability

Conclusion

22. Is there anything you would like to add? Do you have any questions or remarks?

23. Would you be interested in receiving the results of the study by email?

Examples of coding process:

Adapted and translated excerpt of a response to Question 13: “As a developer I need these links because I do not know the specification by heart, so that I could create these links by myself. Because the specification is so large, so you easily lose the overview.”

Applied code: **Perceived Tracing Purpose** – derived subcode: “**Helps developers to maintain overview for large specifications**”

Adapted and translated excerpt of a response to Question 8: “We generally work with Confluence as a collaboration tool and with Jira as a ticket and project management tool. We do very very much in Confluence, the whole specification work etc. and we use Confluence, e.g., for [change request] proposals to generate PDFs from it and send it to the customer. Effort estimations are done in an Excel template and sometimes we use Word, as well.”

Applied codes: **Artifact Types** – derived subcodes: “**specification**”, “**change request**”, “**effort estimation**”

Tools to manage / store Requirements – derived subcodes: “**Confluence**”, “**Jira**”, “**Excel**”, “**Word**”

The subcodes were then subsequently merged where content overlapped and overarching subcategories could be found.